
The Urs of Syed Mohammad Hossain Shah: A Sufi Festival of Folk Belief and Human Unity

Author- **Md Osman Sekh**

Research Scholar , Dept. Of History, Seacom Skills University , Kendradangal, Bolpur, Birbhum .

Prof. Dr Biswarup Goswami

Dept.of History, Seacom Skills University , Kendradangal, Bolpur, Birbhum. Pin 731236.

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17314580>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 17-09-2025

Published: 10-10-2025

Keywords:

Husaini Lineage, Sufi, Pir, Karishunda, Urs Festival, Miraculous Deeds, Murid, Dargah.

ABSTRACT

The Pir culture, miraculous deeds, and role in communal harmony of Hazrat Syed Husain Shah Kirmani (R.A.) of Karishunda village in Bankura district, West Bengal, have been analyzed in this paper. The Urs festival becomes a meeting ground for devotees from both Hindu and Muslim communities, where people participate beyond religious differences. The saint's miracles and humane qualities have earned deep faith and respect in the rural society. This festival is not just about spirituality, but also symbolizes social harmony and human bonding. This paper presents an analytical discussion of how the concept of "Unity in Diversity" is reflected through this festival

Introduction

The annual Urs celebration of Hazrat Syed Mohammad Husain Shah Kirmani (R.A.), held with grandeur in Karishunda village of Bankura district, West Bengal, serves as a remarkable testament to interfaith harmony. This spiritually significant event draws thousands of participants from diverse religious, cultural, and social backgrounds, transforming the village into a profound space of collective devotion and human unity. Karishunda, under the jurisdiction of Indas Police Station, is a culturally enriched and historically rooted village.

Sufism, or Tasawwuf, emerged in the early phase of Islam in Arabia. The term “Sufi” is derived from Ahl al-Suffa—a group of devout companions of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) who practiced asceticism and spiritual contemplation near the Prophet’s Mosque in Medina. In the Indian subcontinent, Sufi saints, fakirs, dervishes, and pirs played a pivotal role in the dissemination of Islam, not through conquest, but through compassion, wisdom, and service. The term Pir (from Persian, meaning “elder” or “wise one”) refers to a spiritual guide who leads seekers on the path toward divine proximity. In classical Islamic thought, such figures are revered as Awliya (friends of God), Murshid (spiritual mentor), or Shaykh (teacher of the path). The loyalty and devotion to the Pir is comparable to the devotion to the Guru among the Hindus. In other words, the Pir-sadhana in Bengal was in a way an Islamic form of Hindu Guruism. (Bandyopadhyay,1986,p-39) In the context of Bengal, the contribution of Sufis to the spread of Islam is of immense historical significance. Unlike conservative theologians (ulama), the liberal and humanistic approach of the Sufis had a profound influence on the local population. Their gentle demeanor, spiritual depth, and emphasis on universal love inspired countless individuals in Bankura and across Bengal to embrace Islamic ideals based on inner transformation and ethical living. In the Bankura District Gazetteer written by O’Malley in 1908, he made reference to the presence of eight Pir dargahs (shrines of Sufi saints) within the Indas Police Station jurisdiction.² These are:

1. Role Shah Madar.
2. Chichingar Shah Bandagi Mustafa.
3. Syed Mohammad Husain of Karishunda.
4. Shah Kabir.
5. Satya Pir of Hayatnagar.
6. Bura Pir of Chaksukur.
7. Shah Bandagi of Bihar.
8. Shah Ismailganj Lashkar of Lakhipur.

In addition, O’Malley mentions two more Pir sites—one at Fakirberia in Gangajalghati and another at Patharchati in Kotulpur. He also refers to the shrine of Shah Qurban Ali in Bishnupur.(O’Malley, L. S. S. 1908,P49). Among these revered Sufi saints, one particularly distinguished figure was Hazrat Syed Husain Shah Kirmani (R.A.). Motivated by the mission of spreading Islam, he is believed to have

migrated from Kirman, a town in Baghdad, Iraq, to the village of Karishunda in Bankura. The religious ceremony observed on the death anniversary of a saint is known as Urs. At Karishunda, the Urs of Hazrat Husain Shah Kirmani (R.A.) is held in the sacred precincts of his dargah (shrine) with deep reverence and spiritual devotion.(Chaudhury, R. M. 2003).On this day, the shrine courtyard transforms into a space of profound serenity and spiritual radiance—devotees wear gentle smiles, and a sense of inner peace fills their hearts. A unique human bond emerges through this collective participation. Transcending religious boundaries, people gather here, drawn by the pull of faith and the call of the heart. This Urs is not merely a religious ritual; it stands as a symbol of humanity, harmony, and spiritual unity.

Location:

Located in Karishunda village of Indas police station in Bankura district of West Bengal, two holy shrines are important symbols of the religious and historical heritage of the place. These two shrines are of Syed Shah Hussain Kirmani (RA) and his son Shah Kabir respectively. The shrine of Syed Shah Hussain Kirmani (RA) is located on the eastern bank of a water body known as “Sheikh Pond”. The present building of this shrine was reconstructed in 1998. The main initiator of the renovation of the shrine was a prominent person from the Hussaini dynasty, Professor Dr. Syed Habibur Rasool. He was a former professor and head of the Department of Geology of Aligarh Muslim University. The shrine is located in a low domed brick building, inside which the grave is very beautifully preserved. The main door faces south. On the other hand, the shrine of Shah Kabir, the son of Syed Shah Hussain, is located on the northeastern bank of the Sheikh Pond. He was unmarried and died during the lifetime of his father.

Shrine of Hazrat Hossein Shah Kirmani (Rahmatullah)

These two shrines are the focus of religious devotion and passion for the local people. In addition, these places are also important for history lovers and researchers, as they are silent witnesses to the spread of Muslim saints and Sufi culture. (Ruhul Amin, S. H. ,2024, January 11)

Genealogy:

The Hussain Shahi dynasty is a prestigious name in the Islamic Sufi tradition. The most respected Pir of this dynasty is the famous Auliya Keram of Baghdad, Ghausul Azam Hazrat Sheikh Abdul Qadir Jilani (RA). He was a direct descendant of Imam Hussain (RA), the grandson of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH). One of the subordinates of Sheikh Abdul Qadir Jilani (RA) was the great Pir of Baghdad, Syed Mohsin Al Hamami Al Khomeini Kirmani, who is one of the most revered figures in the spiritual legacy of this Hussain dynasty. His descendant Syed Abdullah Kirmani later started living in the village of Kusthigiri in Birbhum district of India.

A prominent figure in this spiritual lineage was Syed Shah Mohammad Husain, who laid the foundation of the Husaini lineage in Karishunda village under Indas Police Station of Bankura district. He was a descendant of Syed Abdullah Kirmani of Kushtigiri. Eventually, he passed away in Karishunda itself, where his sacred shrine (mazar) still stands today as a revered site of devotion for the local faithful. The spiritual heritage and religious leadership of the Husaini lineage continue to play a significant role in the religious and cultural life of the local community to this day.

Arrival Date:

Although the exact year and date of Syed Shah Hussain Kirmani's (RA) arrival in Karishunda is not known, there are two opinions among the local Khadems. According to one Khadem, Syed Ruhul Amin, he arrived in Karishunda about five hundred years ago, i.e. during the Hussain Shahi period (16th century). On the other hand, Haji Abdul Ghani believes that he arrived during the reign of the Mughal Emperor Aurangzeb (1658–1707 AD). Although there is disagreement about the time of arrival, both Khadems agree that Syed Shah Hussain did not come to the region for any military purpose. He came for a purely religious purpose—to peacefully propagate and spread Islam.

After coming to this region, he acquired about 2,222 bighas of uncultivated land from the contemporary Malla king of Bishnupur. Based on this land, he transformed the village of Karishunda into a well-organized township. He brought one family each from different professions and castes—such as

Brahmins, washermen, barbers, fishermen, blacksmiths, potters, Moiras, cobblers, Majis, Tilis, and Kalus—and settled them in the village. He donated 22 bighas of land to each family. As a result of his generous and non-communal approach, Karishunda became an integrated, densely populated, and culturally diverse village. As a result of this stingy policy of land donation, the land of the descendants of the Pir family has reduced to only four to five bighas today. As a result, it would not be an exaggeration to call them landless.

Presently, the Muslim residents of Karishunda village are divided into six neighborhoods. Their surnames are: Sheikh, Munshi, Mir, Khondakar, Molla and Midya, Mandal, Mallik. Notably, the last three surnames prove that they were formerly Hindus and later converted to Islam. This is a great example of Syed Shah Hussain's religious influence, humanitarian outlook and social-building activities.

Syed Shah Hussain Kirmani's (RA) miraculous deeds and impact on the public mind:

Many miraculous stories related to the life and works of Syed Shah Hussain Kirmani (RA) are still popular in Karishunda and the surrounding areas. These incidents reveal his spiritual powers and his closeness to Allah, which deeply influenced the local community

According to one such legend, once the Malla king of Bishnupur was going towards Burdwan with a procession of horsemen and elephants. On the way, when he reached a field adjacent to Karishunda, the king's elephant and horse suddenly sat down on the ground and did not want to move forward. Later, on investigation, it was found that a Muslim saint—Syed Shah Hussain—was praying nearby. After his worship was over, the elephant and horse started moving again when he gave permission. Witnessing this miraculous event, the Malla king became very respectful towards the Sufi saint Syed Shah Hussain and, in gratitude, donated about 2,222 bighas of uncultivated land to the Pir Sahib.(Chaudhury, Rathindra Mohan, 2012).

Several other incidents of the miraculous powers of Syed Shah Hussain Kirmani (Rahmatullah Alaihi) are ingrained in the public mind. His son Kabir once uprooted the cucumber tree in the house of a washerman (Rajak) as a child. When the angry Rajak went to complain to Pir Sahib, he calmly said, “You go back, everything will be fine.” When Rajak returned, he saw that the cucumber tree had blossomed and was decorated with more fruits than before. In addition, he had planted mangoes on the mango tree at an untimely time at the request of his disciples. Which is still considered a miracle story by the local people.

Through all these miracles or miraculous events, Syed Shah Hussain Kirmani (RA) was established not only as a preacher of Islam, but also as a spiritual saint with miraculous powers. All these miraculous acts of his greatly influenced the people of Bankura and Bengal at that time. Therefore, even after his death, numerous disciples, regardless of Hindus or Muslims, from different parts of Bengal come to the Urs festival. Which was an indication of the continuous respect and love for this Sufi saint.(Abdul Gani, S. H. ,2024, January 11).

Urs Festival:

A grand religious festival—Urs Sharif—is organized every year on the death anniversary of Pir Hazrat Syed Shah Hussain Kirmani (RA) of Karishunda village. The main Urs festival is celebrated on 7th Falgun, which is the death anniversary of Pir Sahib. Apart from this, three other days—12th Chaitra, 16th Chaitra, and 24th Chaitra—are celebrated on the occasion of the Urs festival.

This festival is not only a religious event, but it is a shining example of Hindu-Muslim communal harmony. Every year, thousands of devotees from different parts of Bengal—Bankura, Burdwan, Hooghly, Howrah, Medinipur, and even from Bihar and Uttar Pradesh—participate in this festival. Numerous devotees come from villages around Karishunda. Numerous people from different parts of the district such as Ketherdanga, Machantala, Eidgamahalla, Chhatna, Panishol, Pathardoba, Rajpur, Bishnupur, Dwarika, Shyamsundarpur, Hatasuria, Katabandh, Ulai, Fakirdanga, Naldanga, Rautkhand, Jamdighari, Narkeldanga, Saltora, etc. join the Urs festival. Besides, numerous devotees from Galsi, Raina, Shyamsunder in Burdwan, Dashghara in Hooghly, Bauria in Howrah, Keshpur in Midnapore, Peardanga, Ambaur, Ramjibanpur, Taratala in Kolkata, etc. participated in the Urs festival. Many people from other areas also joined the festival. Due to such a large crowd, the Urs festival is celebrated for four days.

Syed Ruhul Amin, the successor of Syed Kudrat Kamal, who is the tenth Khadem of this lineage, has been performing the main Urs on 7th Falgun. On this day, fish, rice, tied coffee jhal and moong dal tabaruk are served to the devotees. Due to the presence of both Hindu and Muslim communities, meat is not served. 25 to 30 thousand devotees gather. Syed Shamsul Huda Sahib was the main in-charge of the 12th Chaitra Urs, currently it is performed by his son Syed Ruhul Huda. About 15-20 thousand devotees participate on this day. Separate food arrangements are made for Hindu and Muslim devotees here - beef for Muslims and fish and rice for Hindus. The Hindus of the village themselves take the responsibility of cooking and entertaining the Hindu guests, and they consider it "their own festival". The "Shol Ana" of Karishunda village celebrates the Urs on 16th Chaitra. About 10-12 thousand devotees participate. Here

too, all the arrangements for the food of the devotees are made by the village. Syed Ghulam Ahmad and his descendant Manik are in charge of the 24th Chaitra Urs. On this day too, about ten thousand devotees gather and a fish and rice tabaruk is served at night

The Urs festival under the supervision of the Hossaini family is celebrated over four days instead of just one, primarily due to the overwhelming number of devotees and partly due to internal divisions within the family. Different branches of the family now observe the Urs on separate days, with three days being hosted individually by different factions and one day marked collectively as the “Solana Urs” by the entire village. This division has also been influenced by the prospect of receiving generous offerings from devotees, leading to competition among the descendants of Hossain Shah. Despite this split, the spiritual heritage of Syed Mohammad Hossain Shah remains deeply revered, as countless devotees still gather with heartfelt devotion, almost like ecstatic mystics. The total expense of food and arrangements during the four days is about 3.5 lakh rupees, while the donations collected range between 6.5 to 7 lakh rupees, with the surplus remaining with the respective custodians (khadems). The festival is supported spontaneously by the police, local administration, political figures, and both Hindu and Muslim residents of Karishunda and neighboring villages. Notably, Hindu devotees play active roles in organizing the event, with individuals like Banshi Majhi, Sukumar Pandit, Kartik Pandit, Manik De, and Shanti Prasad Roy taking responsibility with the same devotion as they show during their own religious festivals. The main attraction across the four days is the Islamic gatherings and spiritual sermons, which run from evening until midnight, featuring religious discourses from the Qur’an and Hadith delivered by renowned scholars from districts like Murshidabad, Malda, and Medinipur, including Maulana Meheboob Ali Chishti and Mufti Nurul Arefin. Disciples listen with deep concentration, seeking to connect spiritually with the Divine. After the spiritual sessions and communal meals, locals return home while visitors stay overnight. Unlike many other shrines, this Urs does not include Qawwali or folk Sufi music, giving it a unique spiritual tone. However, during the festival days, a local fair is held with sweet shops, toy stalls, and tea vendors, providing livelihood to many and contributing to the local economy. (Rezanul Haque, S. 2024, January 11).

Devotees' faith and trust in the Pir:

The faith and respect of the devotees towards the Pir of Karishunda, Hazrat Syed Shah Hussain Kirmani (R.A.) is deep and sincere. In the eyes of the devotees, he is the 'Satya Pir', who is deeply believed to fulfill their desires if they seek refuge in him. People from both Hindu and Muslim communities come to this shrine to offer prayers and make vows in the hope of fulfilling various vows

and wishes. Every day of the week, especially Thursday and Friday, the shrine is crowded with devotees. (Moniruddin, S. 2024, January 12).

Devotees offer sweets like batasha, fruits, flowers, candles, and incense sticks at the shrine as tokens of devotion. Once, there was a tradition of dedicating clay horses, though this custom has now nearly disappeared. Women, seeking healing from illnesses or the blessing of children, often bathe in the pond adjacent to the shrine before approaching the mazar with offerings as part of their vows (manat). Traditionally, devotees present hadia or monetary offerings, and many receive spiritually blessed water (panipora) or oil in the hope of attaining the saint's blessings. It is also common for followers to obtain tabeez or amulets from the custodians (khadems). Over time, the relationship between devotees and the shrine has evolved beyond just seeking physical healing or fulfillment of wishes—it has deepened into a spiritual connection, with many becoming formally initiated as disciples (murid) under the guidance of the custodians. A particularly notable feature of this shrine is that, although Islamic practice generally discourages men and women praying together, the deeply spiritual atmosphere of the Karishunda shrine allows both men and women to sit together in meditation, in the sanctum and veranda alike. This unique practice has elevated the shrine beyond being a conventional religious site, transforming it into a space of universal spiritual communion.

Conclusion:

In view of the above discussion, we can say that the Urs festival of Hazrat Syed Hussain Shah Kirmani (R.A) of Karishunda is not only a religious event, but it has become a universal human gathering festival. Devotees of both Hindu and Muslim communities participate spontaneously in this festival, which is a unique example of religious tolerance and inter-communal harmony existing in our society.

This Urs festival transcends religious divisions or formalities and is based on human understanding, sincerity and spiritual passion. Devotees come here with the desire to fulfill their desires and attain the presence of God. In this context, the Urs festival takes shape as an effective reflection of 'unity in diversity' and 'pursuit in harmony'. Therefore, it can be said that this Urs festival of Karishunda is not just a religious ritual, but a platform of communal harmony, where the differences of religion, caste and race disappear. Such festivals spread the message of human connection, harmony and peaceful coexistence in our society and further strengthen the pluralistic spirit of Indian cultural heritage.

Reference

1. Bandyopadhyay, A. C. (1986). *Modhyejuge Bangla o Bangali* (p. 39). K.P. Bagchi & Company.

2. O'Malley, L. S. S. (1908). Bankura District Gazetteer (pp. 49–50). Calcutta: Bengal Secretariat Book Depot.
3. Chaudhury, R. M. (2003). Bankura janer itihās o sanskriti (2nd ed.).
4. Chaudhury, R. M. (2012). Bakurar Musalman.
5. Yunus, M. (2024, January 8). Personal interview. Naldanga.
6. Ruhul Amin, S. H. (2024, January 11). Personal interview. Karishunda.
7. Abdul Gani, S. H. (2024, January 11). Personal interview. Karishunda.
8. Rezanul Haque, S. (2024, January 11). Personal interview. Krishunda.
9. Moniruddin, S. (2024, January 12). Personal interview. Jinkora High Madrasa.